

Adsorption by Titanium Hydroxide Sol.

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Titanium hydroxide sol was first prepared by Graham (*Phil. Trans.*, 1861, 181, 218) by adding hydrochloric acid into sodium titanate solution. Recently Majumdar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 357) has prepared the sol by dropping titanium tetrachloride in water. The free hydrochloric acid was removed by dialysis but it was found that the sol precipitated before the chloride ion was completely removed from the colloidal solution. In the investigations to be described in this paper, titanium hydroxide sol was prepared by adding titanium tetrachloride to distilled water. The mixture was kept in a bath (18°) during the precipitation and was allowed to dialyse at the room temperature. With continued dialysis the sol becomes unstable as the following experimental results for coagulation with potassium chloride and potassium sulphate will show.

TABLE I.

2 C.c. of the sol are taken each time.

Total volume=5 c.c. Time= $\frac{1}{2}$ hour.

Concentration of the sol. TiO_2 per litre.	Time of dialysis in hours.	Electrolyte necessary for coagulation.		Viscosity at 80°.	p_H value.
		N/5-KCl	N/250-K ₂ SO ₄ .		
15.68 g.	48	2.10 c.c.	0.85 c.c.	0.00908	2.1
15.44	72	1.25	0.70	0.01042	2.5
15.26	96	0.85	0.45	0.01228	2.8
15.02	128	0.10	0.40	0.01497	3.5

The viscosities and the hydrogen ion concentrations* of the sols were also measured and are recorded in the above table. It will also be seen from our results that as the sol becomes unstable with the decreasing concentration of hydrogen ions, the ratio of the coagulating powers of KCl and K_2SO_4 diminishes and the viscosity of the sol increases. In one of our papers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 326) we have shown that the precipitation values (P) of ions of different valencies can be expressed by the following modified equation of Whetham :

$$P_1 : P_2 : P_3 = 1 : \frac{1}{2}a : \frac{1}{3}a^2,$$

where $a = e - \frac{q^2}{Dr} / kT$, where q is the electrical charge on the colloid particles, e is the electronic charge, D is the dielectric constant, r the distance of double layer, T is the absolute temperature and k , the Boltzmann constant. Hence as the electrical charge on the colloid particles of titanium hydroxide sol gradually diminishes on continued dialysis, the sol becomes more and more viscous and the ratio of the coagulating powers of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions gradually decreases to approach the limiting value of 1 : 2. The sol becomes very unstable when the p_H value is 4.1 and the hydroxide sets to a jelly within the parchment bag, when the dialysis of the sol is carried on further.

These results, therefore, prove that the presence of hydrogen ions is essential for the stabilisation of positively charged titanium hydroxide sol. The sol thus prepared of p_H value 3.9 was found to appreciably adsorb anions and accordingly some experiments were carried out on the adsorption of anions. For this purpose 10 c. c. of titanium hydroxide sol were taken in small Jena-glass bottles and 40 c.c. of electrolytes of various concentrations were added. The sol was coagulated and the whole mixture was thoroughly shaken and kept for 20 hours to attain equilibrium. The clear liquid at the top of the precipitate was next analysed and thus the concentration of the anion after adsorption was determined.

* The viscosities were measured after the method of Farrow (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 347) and the hydrogen ion concentrations were determined by the indicator method using nitrophenols.

TABLE II.

Concentration of the sol = 15.02 g. TiO_2 per litre.

Amount of sol taken = 10 c.c. Total volume = 50 c.c. Time = 20 hours.

Original conc. in moles per litre.	Final conc. in moles per litre.	Amount adsorbed in millimoles per g. adsorbent.	Original conc. in moles per litre.	Final conc. in moles per litre.	Amount adsorbed in millimoles per g. adsorbent.
<i>Adsorption of chloride ions from KCl.</i>			<i>Adsorption of bromide ions from KBr.</i>		
0.3000	0.2920	0.2660	0.3000	0.2950	0.1660
0.2000	0.1924	0.2530	0.2000	0.1954	0.1680
0.1000	0.0936	0.2190	0.1000	0.0960	0.1830
0.0500	0.0452	0.1590	0.0500	0.0472	0.0990
<i>Adsorption of nitrite ions from KNO_2.</i>			<i>Adsorption of iodate ions from KIO_3.</i>		
0.0910	0.0820	0.299	0.0750	0.0737	0.0432
0.0610	0.0530	0.266	0.0500	0.0487	0.0432
0.0305	0.0240	0.216	0.0250	0.0238	0.0999
0.0153	0.0102	0.172	0.0125	0.0166	0.0990
<i>Adsorption of hydroxyl ions from KOH.</i>			<i>Adsorption of chromate ions from K_2CrO_4.</i>		
0.1200	0.1190	0.0802	0.0400	0.0392	0.0265
0.0800	0.0792	0.0266	0.0200	0.0194	0.0199
0.0400	0.0394	0.0199	0.0100	0.0095	0.0166
0.0200	0.0197	0.0099	0.0050	0.0047	0.0099
<i>Adsorption of dichromate ions from $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.</i>			<i>Adsorption of sulphate ions from K_2SO_4.</i>		
0.0320	0.0295	0.0632	0.3000	0.2905	0.312
0.0213	0.0192	0.0698	0.2000	0.1912	0.292
0.0107	0.0094	0.0432	0.1000	0.0923	0.256
0.0054	0.0049	0.0166	0.0500	0.0443	0.189

Original conc. in moles per litre.	Final conc. in moles per litre.	Amount adsorbed in millimoles per g. adsorbent.	Original conc. in moles per litre.	Final conc. in moles per litre.	Amount adsorbed in millimoles per g. adsorbent.
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Adsorption of thiosulphate ions from Na₂S₂O₃.

0.1430	0.1378	0.173
0.0950	0.0895	0.183
0.0475	0.0439	0.119
0.0238	0.0214	0.079

Adsorption of ferricyanide ions from K₃Fe(CN)₆.

0.3000	0.2882	0.392
0.2000	0.1885	0.362
0.1000	0.0890	0.333
0.0500	0.0420	0.266

Original concentration in moles per litre.

Final concentration in moles per litre.

Amount adsorbed in millimoles per g. adsorbent.

Adsorption of ferrocyanide ions from K₄Fe(CN)₆.

0.0750	0.0718	0.106
0.0500	0.0474	0.086
0.0250	0.0233	0.056
0.0125	0.0116	0.008

From the above tables and Fig. 1, we find that the adsorption of different anions by titanium hydroxide sol is in the following decreasing order :

$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6''' > \text{NO}_2' > \text{SO}_4'' > \text{S}_2\text{O}_3''' > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7''' > \text{Br}' > \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6''' > \text{IO}_3' > \text{CrO}_4'' > \text{OH}'$, when the amounts of adsorption are expressed in millimoles per gram of adsorbent. We have also investigated the coagulation as well as the gelation of titanium hydroxide sol by these anions. The coagulation point has been determined by noting the appearance of flocculation in the sol after half an hour of the addition of electrolyte. It was found that the sol also sets to a jelly by the addition of electrolytes and the gelation values were determined immediately after the addition of the electrolyte. The following results were obtained :

Final concentration in moles.

FIG. 1.

TABLE III.

Sol taken = 3 c.c. Total volume = 4 c.c. Time = $\frac{1}{2}$ hour.

Electrolyte.	Precipitation values in moles.	Gelation values in moles.
KJl	0.00800	0.00350
KBr	0.00450	0.00500
KIO ₃	0.00050	0.00075
KNO ₃	0.00125	—
KOH	0.00013	—
K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	0.00030	0.00050
K ₂ CrO ₄	0.00040	0.00050
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₈	0.00060	0.00100
H ₂ SO ₄	0.00035	0.00050
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	0.00010	0.00012
K ₂ Fe(CN) ₆	0.00008	0.00008

The above table shows that the coagulating powers of the different anions were in the following decreasing order :

Best jellies were obtained when the gelation was effected by monovalent electrolytes possessing low coagulating powers. The gels synerised very quickly after the addition of the electrolyte. The polyvalent anions possessing greater coagulating powers, possess a greater synerising effect. Our experimental results on the coagulating powers of the different anions by titanium hydroxide sol, show that the Schulze-Hardy law, i.e., the greater the valency of an anion, the greater is its coagulating power is applicable, except in the case of OH^- ion which possesses coagulating power greater than bivalent $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ion. It may be of interest to note that OH^- ion possesses a great coagulating effect on several positively charged hydroxide sols like those of Fe(OH)_3 , Cr(OH)_3 , Al(OH)_3 , etc.

In one of the communications (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 830) from these laboratories it has been suggested that the high coagulating power of the OH^- ions for the positively charged sols stabilised by hydrogen ions is due to the removal of hydrogen ions by the introduction of OH^- ions. Iodate ions also possess a greater coagulating power than that of other monovalent ions and it approaches the coagulating power of the bivalent anion $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$. Similar results have been obtained by Weiser and Middleton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 30) with iodate ions and the positively charged sol of Fe(OH)_3 .

We are of the opinion that this behaviour of iodate ions arises out of their tendency to remain in the polymerised condition in solution and thus the iodate ion behaves as a bivalent anion. Very recently Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 585) has also come to the same conclusion from the coagulation experiments and other considerations.

It has been already shown by us that the interpretation of the Schulze-Hardy law that the greater the valency of an ion, greater is its amount of adsorption is not true (compare *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 457; 1926, 30, 628). Our experimental results on the coagulation and adsorption with titanium hydroxide sol show that the tetravalent anion Fe(CN)_6^{4-} which possesses a very high coagulating power is comparatively less adsorbed than several anions of lower valency.

Freundlich (*Kolloid Z.*, 1907, 1, 321), Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 955) and others have assumed that greater the adsorbility of an ion, the greater will be its coagulating power. This assumption seems apparently reasonable specially with the ions of the same valency because along with the electrical attraction of the oppositely charged ions towards the sol particles, the chemical affinity between the sol and the coagulating ion may help in the coagulation of a sol because we know that the greater the chemical affinity of an ion towards an absorbent the greater is its adsorbility. We have, however, shown that the experimental evidence available in this line does not support this assumption. With titanium hydroxide sol, the coagulating power of bivalent and monovalent anions are in the following decreasing order :

Monovalent anions $\text{OH} > \text{IO}_3 > \text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl} > \text{Br}$.

Bivalent anions $\text{SO}_4 > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_4 > \text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.

The amount of adsorption of these bivalent and monovalent anions are in the following decreasing order :

Monovalent anions $\text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{IO}_3$.

Bivalent anions $\text{SO}_4 > \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 > \text{CrO}_4$.

From these experimental results, therefore, we come to the conclusion that even for the anions of the same valency greater adsorption does not necessarily result in a greater coagulating power and hence the views of Freundlich, Bancroft and Weiser are not correct.

We have found that titanium hydroxide sol preferentially adsorbs more of an anion than a cation with the liberation of OH^- ions, which decreases the hydrogen ion concentration of the sol, thus the pH value of the original sol was increased from 3.9 to 7.3 by addition of 10 c.c. of *N*-potassium sulphate solution to 10 c.c. of titanium hydroxide sol. In one of the communications (*loc. cit.*) from these laboratories it has been shown that substances like MnO_2 , SiO_2 etc., adsorb more of cation than anion because of their acid character, whilst substances like $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ etc., adsorb large quantity of anions because of their basic character. Our results, therefore, confirm that titanium hydroxide sol, also known as titanous acid, is

more basic than acidic because it preferentially adsorbs a cation with liberation of OH' ions. This conclusion is further supported by the fact that OH' ions are adsorbed in very small amounts by titanium hydroxide sol.

Majumdar (*loc. cit.*) has observed that a titanium hydroxide sol becomes stable towards the action of electrolytes when it is allowed to age. We have also obtained similar results on the ageing of titanium hydroxide sol. It has been, however, shown in an investigation (compare *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1564) from these laboratories that the sols of substances like $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ etc., have a tendency to become unstable on keeping because these substances lose their adsorption capacities on ageing and hence the adsorbed H^+ , Fe^{+++} , Cr^{+++} , Al^{+++} ions, which are the stabilisers of these sols are given out by these sols. This causes a decrease in the electric charge on the sols and consequently their stability. Whilst the sols of the substances like mastic, gum dammar, gamboge etc., become stable on keeping because these sols are hydrolysed giving out products of the hydrolysis, which are the stabilisers. Hence the content of the stabilisers increases with the age of the sol rendering them more stable. It therefore seems that the behaviour of titanium hydroxide sol, which is positively charged, is different from that of the positively charged sols like $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ etc. We have, therefore, carried out an investigation on the ageing of the titanium hydroxide sol prepared in the cold and in the hot conditions and the following results were obtained.

TABLE IV.

(Sol prepared at 18°.)

Concentration of the sol = 14.3 g. of TiO_2 per litre.

Date.	Electrolyte necessary to coagulate in c.c.		Viscosity at 30.	Sp. conductivity ($\times 10^{-4}$).
	N/20-KCl	N/500-K ₂ SO ₄		
2.8.1929	0.85	0.75	0.01188	2.95
9.8.1929	0.95	0.75	0.01163	2.88
16.8.1929	1.00	0.80	0.01152	2.94
23.8.1929	1.05	0.80	0.01149	2.92
30.8.1929	1.05	0.82	0.01145	2.90
6.9.1929	1.05	0.80	0.01147	2.90

TABLE V.

(Sol prepared at 55°.)

 Concentration of the sol = 9.22 g. TiO₂ per litre.

Date	Electrolyte necessary to coagulate in c.c.		Viscosity at 30°.	Sp. conductivity. (10 ⁻⁴).
	N/20-KCl	N/500-K ₂ SO ₄ .		
5. 8. 29	0.45	0.50	0.00968	3.12
12. 8. 29	0.45	0.50	0.00967	3.18
19. 8. 29	0.40	0.50	0.00967	3.16
26. 8. 29	0.40	0.45	0.00979	3.17

Our results with the sol of titanium hydroxide sol prepared at 18° show that it (i) becomes stable towards its coagulation by electrolytes like KCl, K₂SO₄, (ii) shows a decrease in the electrical conductivity and (iii) a decrease in the viscosity on ageing. On the other hand a sol of titanium hydroxide prepared at 55° does not show any change in the stability and the specific conductivity and the viscosity increases very little on ageing.

It has been shown in one of our publications (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 48, 43) that the viscosity of a sol increases with the decrease of its electrical charge, whilst the viscosity of the sol decreases with the increase of its electrical charge. Consequently, a decrease in the viscosity of titanium hydroxide sol (prepared at 18°) on ageing shows that the sol is more electrically charged and, therefore, becomes more stable towards its coagulation by electrolytes on ageing. That the electrical charge increases with age can also be shown from the fact that the ratio of the precipitation values of monovalent anion Cl⁻ and bivalent anions SO₄²⁻ increases on keeping the sol prepared at 18°. On the other hand, the sol prepared in the hot condition becomes more viscous on ageing which shows that it gets less electrically charged and hence has a tendency to become unstable. We are, therefore, of the opinion that a sol of titanium hydroxide prepared in the cold becomes stable on keeping as the free HCl present in the sol gradually acts on Ti(OH)₄ forming TiCl₄ which gives out Ti⁴⁺ ions that are completely adsorbed by the sol and hence possesses greater stabilising influence than H⁺ ions. A determination of the electrical conductivity of the sol prepared in the cold shows that the H⁺ ions are removed from the sol

by the process of ageing. This is, however, not possible with a sol prepared at 55° as it is well known that the chemical activity as well as the power of adsorption by a precipitate is considerably diminished when it is prepared in the hot condition. These conclusions are further supported from our measurements of the specific conductivity of the sol.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) A sol of titanium hydroxide prepared by dropping TiCl_4 slowly into water at 18° cannot be completely freed from HCl by dialysis. It was found that the sol containing 15.2 g. TiO_2 per litre on prolonged dialysis gradually became viscous and as soon as the p_H value was more than 4.1 the whole mass coagulated as a gelatinous precipitate.

(2) The sol prepared at 18° adsorbed appreciable amounts of anions from different sodium or potassium salts and they are adsorbed in the following decreasing order :

$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6''' > \text{NO}'_2 > \text{SO}''_4 > \text{Cl}' > \text{S}_2\text{O}_3'' > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7'' > \text{Br}' > \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6'''' > \text{IO}_3' > \text{CrO}''_4 > \text{OH}'$; the amounts of adsorption are expressed in moles per gram adsorbent.

The coagulating powers of different anions are in the following decreasing order :

$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6'''' > \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6''' > \text{OH}' > \text{SO}_4'' > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7'' > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_4'' > \text{IO}_3' > \text{S}_2\text{O}_3'' > \text{NO}'_2 > \text{Cl}' > \text{Br}'$.

(3) The above results show that the generally accepted view that an ion which is highly adsorbed also possesses a high coagulating power is not supported by experiments.

(4) The amount of adsorption of OH' ions by titanium hydroxide sol is very small. The high coagulating power of OH' ions is due to the removal of the stabiliser H^+ ions by OH' ions.

(5) Titanium hydroxide sol adsorbs more of an anion than a cation, with the liberation of OH' ions which increases the p_H value of the sol.

(6) We are of the opinion that titanium hydroxide (also known as titanic acid) possesses more of basic character than acidic.

(7) A sol of titanium hydroxide containing 15.2 g. TiO_2 per litre and prepared at 18° becomes stable towards its coagulation by electrolytes, shows a decrease in the specific conductivity and the viscosity on ageing.

(8) On the other hand a sol of titanium hydroxide containing 10.2 g. TiO_2 per litre and prepared at 55° does not show any change in stability and the specific conductivity and the viscosity increase very slightly on ageing.

(9) We are of the opinion that a sol of titanium hydroxide prepared in the cold becomes stable on keeping as free HCl present in the sol gradually acts on $\text{Ti}(\text{OH})_4$ forming TiCl_4 , which gives out Ti^{4+} ions that are completely adsorbed by the sol and hence possess greater stabilising influence than H^+ ions. This is not possible in the case of the sol prepared at 55° as it is well known that chemical activity as well as power of adsorption of a precipitate is considerably diminished when prepared in the hot condition.

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